
A MAINTENANCE PARADIGM FOR THE POWER INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE 21ST CENTURY NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a total integrated system approach to management and maintenance of the power infrastructure in the 21st century Nigeria. The model discussed here furnishes facility managers with performance/reliability data, technical/financial audit trail, contingency assessment/control measures and effective feedback loops required for sustainable management and maintenance. This approach to power system management moves the traditional time-based maintenance policy to condition-based, reliability centered maintenance policy. The issues discussed are also applicable to other areas of national infrastructure.

KEYWORDS: Power Infrastructure, Maintenance model, Performance data, Contingency assessment, technical auditing, work planning.

INTRODUCTION

The safety and convenience of the general public as well as the development of the national economy depend on the effectiveness of maintenance and management of the infrastructural facilities which are essentially engineering based. Modern conveniences when they work properly are like breathing, no one notices until they go wrong (Maduka, 1997). Hence the paramount importance of proper maintenance of these facilities to the people and the economy. Most especially this is so for the (electric) power sector since it affects the development and maintenance of the other infrastructures. Unfortunately, this very important infrastructure is in a very poor state in our country, Nigeria.

The present dilapidated state of the power infrastructure is attributed to poor maintenance as a result of poor funding between 1982 and 1999 (Makoju, 2003). Recently a lot of money was invested in the power sector with little or nothing to show for it. Thus it is obvious that something extra is needed to improve service delivery in the power sector. In addition to extra funding, a totally integrated system approach to maintenance is needed to eliminate all the clogs in the wheel of maintenance in that sector especially the issues of high technical losses (20%) partly due to (poor) maintenance habit (Okafor and Somolu, 2003).

This paper presents a total integrated system approach to management and maintenance of the power infrastructure in the 21st century Nigeria.

Generally, all physical facilities pass through life cycles that are complex, yet identifiable and definable. The cycle commences with the installation of the new facilities and proceeds through stages of initial use, modification and adaptation to final deterioration and obsolescence resulting in eventual restoration or decommissioning. Thus a good maintenance routine is one that can manage these facilities at an acceptable standard and cost to give reliable services throughout the life cycle. A good maintenance routine should also be sustainable and possess the quality of extending the useful life of a facility and that is what presented in Fig. 1

Fig. 1: Simple Block of Maintenance Model

Components of the Maintenance Model

This model is a chain-link procedure comprising; planning, organizing, directing and controlling processes as detailed below:

Planning: The approach here is preventive and arranges maintenance activities into a work programme whereby 80% of the total maintenance is assigned to preventive maintenance and 20% is devoted to corrective measures. This approach is derived from the Pareto rule which holds that 80% of the problems are associated with 20% of the causes. Hence all maintenance activities are pre-planned, quantified and scheduled to meet with the maintenance objectives. Also, all plausible contingencies are configured and preventive and corrective measures put in place to ensure continuity of service. In this model, all objectives must be specific, measurable, time-phased and realistic. Specificity and realism in making objectives ensures that the goals are achievable. This is very important because unachievable goals impact negatively on workers and may lead to low morale (Stahl, 1995). Objectives may be short term (1 year), medium term (1-5 years), or long term (5 years +). When the actual performance falls short of the objective, corrective actions must be taken with minimal response time to avoid service interruption.

Planning essentially comprises of the following:

i. Inventory of Human Capital

Human resources are the most important component of any effective maintenance routine. The engineer is perhaps the most essential component in the manpower chain of any infrastructure (Nduka, 2003). Planning for human capital includes institution of adequate training and re-training programs to provide staff in all cadres of operation. For example, with the current deregulation exercise in the power sector, there is need for adequate training of technicians, engineers, environmentalists, and public policy experts for the expected expanded power system (Momoh, 2003).

ii. Inventory of facilities and standardization

This is a very important planning tool for effective maintenance. A correct inventory of equipment/facility ensures a correct inventory of spares required for maintenance. Also, standardization plays a big role in maintaining an effective, coordinated and economic system of power supply. This is because standardization leads to close cooperation between the facility managers and the equipment manufacturers resulting in simplification and innovation in plant and equipment which in turn reduces (maintenance) cost and improves performance (Booth, 1977). In the (electric) power sector, standardization could be gainfully applied in the following areas;

- A) Network designs from 11KV to 330KV.
- B) Feeders, tie-lines and cables (low/high voltage).
- C) Transformers, circuit breakers and protection devices

- iii. **Inventory of Required Spares/Consumables and Determination of Re-order Levels**
This is very important for sustainable maintenance especially in the power sector where continuity of service is very essential. Lack of spares has been a major problem in the maintenance of the infrastructure. This is mainly because these parts are not manufactured locally and cannot be ordered off the shelf. A proper inventory of spares coupled with the frequency of maintenance aid in correct determination of re-order levels to ensure that the maintenance schedules are strictly adhered to. For economic management of the hydro power stations correct charts for the withdrawal of water from the dams and lakes must be produced to avoid epileptic operations of these stations.
- iv. **Definition of Tasks or Trades**
This ensures that definite tasks/jobs are assigned to certain trades or expertise. Thus round poles are fitted into round holes and areas lacking in human expertise are easily detected for remedial action.
- v. **Record Keeping**
This involves detailed and comprehensive recording of all performance data during a life span of the equipment and comparing results with the manufacturer's claims. Thus a reliability data needed for scheduled maintenance and for specifying spare parts re-order levels is built up. This data is critical in matching up available capacity to installed capacity in electricity sector and thus in raising the load factor (KWhrs generated as a percentage of designed output rating) which currently stands at an average of 0.4. This record will also help the operators/maintenance engineers in the generating station to manage off-design performance problems on the turbine generators. This could be critical for temperature reversal problems in gas turbine-generators due to frequent outages in the Nigerian power system.
- vi. **Specification of Acceptance Standards**
This is very important for accepting new equipments and must include a maintenance program (minimum of 1 year) to be supervised by a system specialist from the equipment manufacturer. This gives room for critical self examination, adjustment of new equipment and interfacing with already existing ones for smooth operations (Warrick, 1981).

Organizing: This is essentially a work-study activity, which usually results in technology upgrade for faster and more efficient service delivery. All maintenance activities are broken down to the lowest level noting all the interdependences and interconnections. These activities are then analyzed considering many procedures of accomplishment. From the analysis, procedures for carrying out all the activities in the most effective and economic manner are specified. These specifications in form of work programs or even computer software are then produced for the relevant maintenance activities to eliminate time wasting and improper use of time and equipment. Results of activities carried out in this process are regularly fed-back to the planning stage for improved maintenance. This is very crucial for reliability improvement in electric power production. For example, work properly done in this process will definitely show the numerous merits of employing computers for the following.

- i. Power system studies for root-cause analysis, stability, optimal power flow, available transfer capacity (ATC) calculation, etc.
- ii. Production of computer software programs for studying and analyzing characteristics of system components such as boilers, turbine-generators, alternators, transmission and distribution lines and transformers.
- iii. Production of simulation programs to model system operations and to aid improved network designs.
- iv. Data processing for online application expected from expanded operations.

Directing: This is the operations arm of the maintenance model and determines the operating mode of the system. In this model all activities are predicated on Dy Liacco's concept of power system security (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Dy Liacco's Diagram Adapted from Pavella et al

The different operating modes are defined as follows:

- a. Preventive Security Assessment Mode: This concerns the continuous monitoring of the power system to determine its readiness to withstand possible contingencies. All feasible contingencies are simulated and preventive control measures specified so as to maintain operations within the secure region.
- b. Emergency State Detection mode: Emergency control measures are specified to effect fast response to system faults in order to forestall preventive system interruption.
- c. Restorative Mode: In the event of major fault, this mode provides predetermined control measures designed to prevent the growth or cascading of faults which could lead to total system collapse. Mainly, the task here is to minimize (in the case of major faults) the amount of undelivered energy by re-synchronizing lost generation as soon as possible and picking up the disconnected loads in order of priority (Pavella, 2000).

For all routine maintenance activities, the system of work order is prescribed for accountability and good audit trail which are lacking in the power utility. Work orders prepared in consonance with the maintenance objective must be completed for any maintenance activity and these work orders should have the following data:

- i. Nature of activities to enable selection of proper tools.
- ii. Location of activity.
- iii. Exact faulty parts to be replaced (if known).
- iv. Spare parts required from the store.
- v. Appropriate tools required for the activity.
- vi. Transport (if any) required for the activity.
- vii. Route plan if the activity involves conveyance of heavy equipment.
- viii. Name of the officer assigned to do the job.
- ix. Name of the officer authorizing the job.
- x. State of the equipment at the end of the maintenance activity.

The foregoing helps to determine competence levels which must be specified and strictly adhered to in all cases. Controlling: This is the major feedback arm of the maintenance model. It comprises a formal but simple reporting system which includes all the necessary data required to effect management decisions. Thus planning and controlling are usually linked in the first step of determining maintenance objectives. The instant feedback from controlling to directing is for contingency measures required for service continuity.

Controlling, in this model, also includes the following:

- a. Weekly health, safety and environment (HSE) meetings to discuss accidents in the work places and how to prevent them. Written reports of these meetings must be sent to planners as inputs for their planning work.
- b. Weekly reports on facility condition and level of spare parts. The reports are to be properly documented and cross-checked with previous month's reports to form the basis for assessment and control measures.
- c. Monthly reports on maintenance personnel, size and level must be prepared and sent to management for corrective measures to be effected.

ADVANTAGES OF THE PROPOSED MODEL

This model, when installed and properly implemented establishes firmly an organization's maintenance objectives, formulate specific maintenance levels and procedures for accomplishing the same objectives in the most effective and economic manner. The potential benefits of this model to the Nigerian power infrastructure are:

- i. Provision of up to date facility inventory in the power utility. This will eliminate the issues of unwholesome procurement procedures and save enormous cost by making it impossible for the stores to be filled with obsolete and unusable materials and equipment acquired with billions of naira as was the case with the old NEPA stores (NEPA and mandate, 2001).
- ii. Provision of a method of accumulating maintenance data and controlling the quality of operational facility life cycle analysis.

- iii. Provision of preventive maintenance schedule with assigned facility responsibility at the lower level of supervision. This reduces down time due to unplanned maintenance and imposes a great sense of responsibility on every worker.
- iv. Provision of a defined role for maintenance in the power infrastructure which will clearly identify maintenance activities and assign secondary roles to other activities. This makes for good budgeting and rules out misplaced priorities as was the case with NEPA where 50% of the authority's revenue was spent on personnel and overhead cost and very little on the maintenance activities.
- v. Establishment of performance objectives at the maintenance task level and the provision of operational variance reporting at the first level of supervision. This vital function reduces standby time, improves work method and provides appropriate on-the-job training for effective maintenance (Okorie, 1982).
- vi. The use of Intelligent Electronic Devices (IEDs): These are required for the monitoring of the service condition of the power system assets for example; high voltage circuit breakers, power transformers, reactors etc. The IEDs (for improved efficiency) are put in place of electromechanical or static devices for protection, control and measurement operations.

They provide the power system with wide adaptive protection and real-time automatic power restoration procedures (Lohmann, 2009). The areas of application where these devices can contribute in the improvement of the Nigerian power system are; Thermal/Hydro power station operations and management, automation of the sub-stations and real-time, on-line power line monitoring. However, it must be emphasized that the IEDs will perform efficiently only if there is an excellent communication network for the power system.

Also, these devices in form of micro-processors could be used to achieve dynamic load shedding and the islanding of out-of-step areas. It is the author's view that these devices could be excellently employed for system restoration after a collapse i.e. to cover the starting of generators, the establishment of power Blands and their reconnection to restore the rigid system and achieve frequency stabilization in the first shedding step.

Monitoring of electric power systems in real-time for reliability, aging status and presence of incipient faults requires distributed processing of vast amount of data from distributed sensor networks. (Jiang and Manishev, 2009). These are employed as tele-operated robots for live-line maintenance to reduce periods of power outage. This procedure is widely used in countries like Japan, Canada, and Spain etc.

CONCLUSION

A paradigm for effective maintenance of the Nigerian power infrastructure has been discussed bringing out its potential benefits to the decaying power infrastructure. The model is seen as an effective aid to capacity building in maintenance which will definitely yield great dividends if applied to other sectors in the Nigerian economy such as; telecommunications, oil and gas, manufacturing, water and housing. The limitations of this model is envisaged only in the area of implementation since the full benefits could only be attained if all the components are put in place and strictly executed. Bearing in mind the propensity of Nigerian maintenance managers to poor implementation of policies, one may tend to write off the proposed model as one of those models that look good only on paper. This notwithstanding, it is the author's view that the model proposed here even if poorly implemented could still go a long way in reviving the decaying power infrastructure.

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